

GEOLOGY OF RIMAE BODE REGION AS PRIORITY SITE CANDIDATE FOR CHINA'S FIRST CREWED LUNAR MISSION. M. Yang¹, J. Huang¹, W. Iqbal², L. Wueller², C. H. van der Bogert², H. Hiesinger², S. Mikolajewski², M. Xie³, S. Hu⁴, Long Xiao^{1,5}, ¹State Key Laboratory of Geological Processes and Mineral Resources, Hubei Key Laboratory of Planetary Geology and Deep Space Exploration, School of Earth Sciences, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan 430074, China, ²Institut für Planetologie, Universität Münster, Wilhelm-Klemm-Straße 10, 48149 Münster, Germany, ³College of Science, Guilin University of Technology, Guilin 541006, China, ⁴Institute of Geology and Geophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100029, China, ⁵State Key Laboratory of Lunar and Planetary Sciences, Macau University of Science and Technology, Macau 999078, China (junhuang@cug.edu.cn).

Introduction: In 2023, China publicly announced and started its crewed lunar exploration phase program, with plans to achieve Chinese first crewed lunar mission by 2030 (<https://www.cnsa.gov.cn/n6758823/n6758838/c10355400/content.html>). During the selection of potential landing regions, candidates were evaluated based on their scientific significance and engineering feasibility, ultimately narrowing down the possibilities from 106 to 30 prime landing regions [1]. Among these, the Rimae Bode region emerged as a highly ranked candidate due to its high-Ti volcanic deposits, diverse rock types, and favorable conditions for Earth observation [1-3].

Geological Units: The Rimae Bode region, situated between Sinus Aestuum and Mare Vaporum at the lunar mare-highlands boundary (Fig. 1a). In our study area, we identify five distinct geological units including a dark mantle deposit (DMD), mare units in Sinus Aestuum, networks of volcanic rilles including Rimae Bode, and the highlands (Fig. 1b). The DMD is pyroclastic material with relatively low albedo, whose thickness is ranges from 77-136 m. Sinus Aestuum basin is an ancient impact basin filled with low-Ti basaltic lavas. These lava flows have a maximum thickness ranging from 193-1021 m and an absolute model age (AMA) of ~ 2.96 Ga [4]. A 4 m-thick regolith in Sinus Aestuum is primarily composed of local material, with a minor admixture of exotic components sourced mainly from the Copernicus and Eratosthenes craters. The Rima Bode I mare unit (~3.11 Ga) is characterized by sinuous rilles that are potential sources for the basalts in Sinus Aestuum, indicated by the similarity of the spectral characteristics and AMAs. The Rima Bode II mare unit exhibits high abundances of Th and Ti.

Furthermore, we construct a geological column for eastern Sinus Aestuum (Fig. 1c).

Scientific goals: The National Research Council of the National Academies underscored the scientific objectives and significance of lunar exploration [5]. Based on the NRC report, we also have outlined the scientific goals for the Rimae Bode region in Table 1.

The Rimae Bode region, characterized by its diverse volcanic features, offers an exceptional opportunity to explore fundamental questions about lunar volcanism. In particular, the collection and return of

pyroclastic samples from its DMD unit would significantly refine our knowledge of the deep lunar mantle's composition.

Feasible Landing Sites: Based on the geology, we examine proposed four prospective landing sites in the traversable areas (Fig 1a,b). These sites provide a range of diverse geological samples, including volcanic debris, mare basalts, Copernicus crater ejecta, and high-Th materials. Such a collection promises to unveil the geological evolution of the region and enhance our understanding of the lunar mantle composition and volcanic processes.

References: [1] Niu R. et al. (2024) Adv. Astronaut. Sci. Technol., 7, 37–50. [2] Van Der Bogert C. H. et al. (2021) Planet. Sci. J., 2, 84. [3] Hiesinger H. et al. (2021) Lunar Planet. Sci. Conf., 52nd, Abstract #1485. [4] Hiesinger H. et al. (2022) Lunar Planet. Sci. Conf., 53rd, Abstract #2169. [5] National Research Council (2007) The Scientific Context for Exploration of the Moon, National Academies Press.

Fig. 1 Rimae Bode region. (a) LROC WAC mosaic of the study area with proposed landing sites (stars). (b) Simplified geologic map. (c) Conceptual geological

column. The location is indicated by the red star in (a) and (b).

Table 1. Science concepts and goals in Rimae Bode region based on the NRC report [5]. Green represents science goals that can be addressed. The red represents science goals that cannot be addressed.

science goal	a	b	c	d	e
1. Bombardment history of the inner solar system	test cataclysm hypothesis	age of South Pole-Aitken	Establish absolute chronology	recent impact flux	secondary craters
2. Structure and composition of lunar interior	Thickness/variability of lunar crust	Stratification of mantle	Size, composition, state of core	Thermal state of interior	N/A
3. Diversity of lunar crustal rocks	differentiation products	age, distribution, origin of rocks	Composition of lower crust	Complexity of lunar crust	Extent/structure of megaregolith
4. Lunar poles and volatiles	State and distribution of volatiles	Source of volatiles	Transport, alteration, loss, processes	Properties of polar regolith	Polar regolith and ancient solar environment
5. Lunar volcanism	Origin/variability of basalts	Age of mare basalts	Range/extent of pyroclastic deposits	Lunar volcanic flux	N/A
6. impact processes	melt sheet differentiation	Structure of multi-ring impact basins	Crater formation	Mixing of local and ejecta material	N/A
7. Regolith processes	Characterize ancient regolith	Physical properties of regolith	regolith modification processes	Rare minerals in regolith	N/A